

A TRAVEL COST ESTIMATION OF CONSUMER SURPLUS IN RECREATIONAL VISITS: A COUNT MODEL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Recreational services are demanded because they generate benefits. The recreational benefits connected with a destination can be valued based on visitor preferences, which can aid in the formulation of an appropriate Natural Resource Management policy. Environmental and natural resource management studies often attempt to quantify the welfare shift caused by a policy change. In general, welfare is defined as the area under the demand curve; and accordingly, by estimating the demand curve, consumer surplus is obtained, which illustrates the welfare changes connected with an environmental policy change. But unfortunately, conventional markets fail to determine the recreational demand preferences for lack of a proper price mechanism. So the only choice is a non-market method. The Travel Cost Method (TCM) is a well-documented demand-based method in environmental literature for measuring such non-marketed recreational benefits. This study attempts to estimate the consumer surplus, in the recreational demand for the Dibru Saikhowa National Park (DSNP),

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Assam, with the help of TCM. In the process, it also seeks to answer the question of whether the existing user charges of DSNP reflect the true recreational demand assigned to the park by its visitors. The findings of the study are expected to be useful for different stakeholders associated with the park's conservation in general and its recreational services in particular, including policymakers.

KEY WORDS: *Travel cost, consumer surplus, truncation, endogenous stratification, multi-site visitors.*

1. Introduction:

Like all utility bearing goods and services, recreational services also generate benefits. It is the benefit or utility associated with use of a resource for recreational purposes. The benefit people receive from natural resource systems in exchange for activities such as boating, fishing, hunting, trekking, enjoying the scenic beauty etc. are examples of recreational benefits. The recreational benefits connected with a destination can be valued based on visitor preferences, which can aid in the formulation of an appropriate Natural Resource Management policy. Environmental and natural resource management studies frequently attempt to quantify the welfare shift caused by a policy change. In general, welfare is defined as the area under the demand curve; and accordingly, by estimating the demand curve, consumer surplus is obtained, which illustrates the welfare changes connected with an environmental policy change (Gunatilake, 2003).

Unfortunately, determination of recreational demand preferences is not possible through conventional market for lack of a proper price mechanism. This is the very reason why these preferences sometimes go unmeasured or unnoticed. The access to many natural areas with recreational services are typically free and is open to everyone. Some protected areas charge a nominal entry fee but that is far from a fair price for the entire range of recreational services they offer. Furthermore, because these prices are usually set by a regulatory authority, they remain constant throughout a set length of time and between sites of comparable nature. This means that these prices can neither signal scarcity nor capture

fluctuations in actual visitor's demand for recreational services. Therefore, no accurate estimation of the demand function can be made with the conventional techniques. In such a circumstance, the only choice is a non-market method. The Travel Cost Method (TCM) is a well-documented demand-based method in environmental literature for measuring such non-marketed recreational benefits.

1.1 Objective and Research Question:

With the aforesaid ideas in mind, this paper attempts to estimate the consumer surplus, if any, in the recreational demand for the Dibru Saikhowa National Park (DSNP), Assam, with the help of TCM. In the process, it also seeks to answer the question of whether the existing user charges of DSNP reflect the true recreational demand assigned to the park by its visitors.

1.2 Significance of the Study:

Despite the fact that there is a sea of literature on recreational demand estimation on a global scale, the number of works at the national level is still quite low. When it comes to Assam, the picture is even more bleak. Whatever work on recreational demand has been done in the state has largely been limited to the Kaziranga National Park. But being a river island national park, the geographical as well as the ecological characteristics of DSNP are unique and demand special attention. This limits the scope of benefit transfer models. Hence, it would not be appropriate to generalize the results of other recreational studies on this bio-diversity hotspot. One study on estimation of the recreational value of DSNP however is available (Phukon, 2017). But the current study is again expected to be a methodological improvement over the previous study since it addresses a few critical methodological issues that have not been addressed earlier, such as, inclusion of multi-purpose visitors into the sample, estimation of the value of travel time, use of individual travel cost method to allow for inherent variations in the data after taking care of truncation and endogenous stratification etc. The findings of the study are expected to be useful for different stakeholders associated with the park's conservation in general and its recreational services in particular, including policymakers.

1.3 Theoretical Background:

The generic TCM works on a simple economic issue similar to demand preferences for any other good. While taking the decision of visiting a recreational site, individuals have to make a choice of the site they want to visit among many alternative sites. Then they have to incur the cost of travelling to the chosen site. This decision may have to be made a couple of times per year or season. This means the individuals have to decide not just on the site but also on the number of times they want to travel to it. This resembles a simple demand analysis and all the approaches to recreational demand models basically build upon this issue.

The simplest model of a travel cost requires the respondents to maximize a utility function of the form (Kolstad, 2006):

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{x,v} U(x, v, q) \\ \text{subject to, } & wT = x + [p_0 + w(t_t + t_v)]v \\ & \equiv x + p_v v \end{aligned}$$

where,

$p_v = p_0 + w(t_t + t_v)$ and represents total travel cost,

$w =$ wage,

$x =$ a basket of market goods with unitary prices,

$v =$ number of visits to a site,

$q =$ site quality,

$T =$ total time available to devote to travel and work,

$p_0 =$ out of pocket expenses associated with a trip,

$t_t =$ travel time and

$t_v =$ on-site time.

Solving this maximization problem produces a demand function for visit to the park,

$$v = f(p_v, q, y)$$

The goal of every TCM is to estimate some form of this demand function, usually with other socio-economic predictor variables. After estimating the demand function, consumer's surplus of the visitors, which provides their recreational benefit and the recreational value of the site in question, can be computed.

2. The Dibru Saikhowa National Park: A Brief Profile:

The DSNP is a national park in the state of Assam. The name is an amalgamation of the river Dibru that flows through the south and the river port of

Saikhowa in the east. Initially declared as a sanctuary, its status was upgraded to a National Park for the conservation of the White Winged Wood Duck (*Asarcornis scutulata*), the state bird of Assam. It is a part of one of the 19 biodiversity hotspots in the world and is considered to be the only river island National Park in India (Mahanta, 2014). The park also happens to be the largest Salix Swamp forest in the entire north-east India and the second largest river island in the state of Assam, after 'Majuli'. Dibru Saikhowa is also a Biosphere Reserve declared under the aegis of United Nation's Man and Biosphere programme. Sheltering over 500 species of birds, it is an Important Bird Area (IBA) as declared by BNHS (Bombay Natural History Society) and Bird Life International. Some of the birds species are White Winged Wood Duck, Crested Serpent Eagle, Lesser Adjutant Stork, Greater Adjutant Stork, Greater Crested Grebe, Open bill Stork, Large Cormorant, Large Whistling Teal, Black necked Stork, Grey leg Goose, Griffon Vulture, Grey-headed Fishing Eagle, Spot Billed Pelican, Osprey, Greater Spotted Eagle, Great Pied Hornbill, Pale Capped Pigeon, Jerdon's Babbler, Marsh Babbler, Black Breasted Parrot bill, etc. Among mammals, 36 species belonging to 10 orders, 19 families and 27 genera have been recorded so far (Phukon, 2017) many of which are in the IUCN red list of threatened species. A few of the major mammals are Asian Elephant, Leopard, Clouded Leopard, Dhole, Jungle Cat, Sloth Bear, Small Indian Civet, Squirrels, Gangetic river Dolphin, Slow Loris, Assamese Macaque, Pig Tailed Macaque, Rhesus Macaque, Capped Langur, Hoolock Gibbon, Wild boars, Sambar, Hog Deer, Barking Deer, Asiatic Water Buffalo, Feral Horses etc. The park is the only protected area in the entire country with the Feral Horses. Apart from this, DSNP also homes about 104 species of fishes, 105 species of butterflies, 18 species of amphibians, 43 species of reptiles along with a variety of other invertebrates that are yet to be documented (Das, 2011). In case of floral diversity Dibru-Saikhowa has 680 species (295 herbs including aquatic, 155 shrub and under shrub, 126 trees, 81 climbers & twiners, 19 epiphytes, 4 parasites) of flowering plants, 38 species of orchids and many Non-flowering plants that are still not yet properly documented (Das, 2011). Widely diverse and unique in more ways than one, the park is an important tourist destination and very popular among specific interest groups such as bird

watchers, trekkers etc. The best season for visiting the park is October to February end for birds, November to February for trekking, March to May for Orchids and May to August for boat safari. The access to the interior areas of the park is only possible during the summer season when the river channels across the park holds enough water for boat safari. Since the park is surrounded by water from every side, for entry and exit to and from the park, one has to separately hire a registered boat from either Guijan Range office or Saikhowa Range office.

3. Method, Materials and Model

3.1 Method:

TCM considers the cost of travelling to a particular site to be a proxy for the price of that site's recreational services. Individual Travel Cost Method (ITCM) was chosen as the variant of choice for the present study because it offers the advantage of accounting for inherent variation in the data and the ability to estimate the trip generating function with a lower sample size. ITCM essentially involves estimation of a demand function where the quantity demanded would be the visitation rate. In the present study, the visitation rate has been defined as the number of times a visitor has visited DSNP over a span of five years including the current trip, and was regressed on total travel cost, consumption standard index, availability of substitute sites and a few other socio-demographic control variables. Attempts have also been made to estimate the opportunity cost of travel time with the help of a stated preference technique, and to compute the travel cost of multi-site visitors with the help of 'rank-reciprocal' method. This makes the definition of travel cost in the present study more inclusive and comprehensive. Finally, the sample mean consumer's surplus have been calculated and aggregated over the target population to arrive at the estimated recreational value figure.

3.2 The Sample:

The data for TCM were obtained through structured interview schedules from visitors of DSNP who visited the park during 2017-18. The sample was drawn from on-site visitors. A total of 211 visitors were chosen at random from the park's two entry points, Guijan ghat and Saikhowa ghat. Given that the park is typically

accessible to visitors throughout the year, data were collected in many rounds in an attempt to capture the complete tourist season. Attempts were also made to sample at random times of the day and on random days of the week in order to choose respondents from a diverse range of backgrounds and to create a more representative sample.

3.3 The Model and Its Estimation:

TCM attempts to quantify a site's recreational demand, and on-site sampling is commonly employed for this purpose. As a technique, on-site sampling ensures that the survey is conducted with users. There are numerous empirical applications of on-site sampling in TCM. Khan (2006), Heberling and Templeton (2009), Emiriya et al. (2013), Limaiei et al. (2014), and Bhatt and Bhat (2016) are a few examples. As a technique, on-site sampling is more time and resource efficient than a survey of the entire population, especially when just a small proportion of the population participates in site activities (Haab and McConnell, 2002). With these considerations in mind, the current study also employs an on-site sampling strategy.

Choosing the ideal model for on-site sampling necessitates resolving a few analytical issues, the most notable of which are *Truncation* and *Endogenous Stratification*.

Truncation is a problem that comes with on-site sampling. With an on-site sample, we can observe only those people who have made at least one trip to the location in question. The sample is truncated at zero since all observed units of the sample have taken at least the current trip and those who have not taken any are not observed (Espineira and Tuffour, 2008). In this situation, the dependent variable is a count variable, as it is a non-negative integer with values equal to the number of visitors to the site in question. The demands for the observed sample units would be truncated or would contain an error known as truncated error (Haab and McConnell, 2002).

Endogenous stratification occurs because sampling on-site frequently results in what is known as choice-based sampling or size-bias, also known as avidity bias, because frequent visitors are more likely to be sampled than infrequent

visitors (Espineira and Tuffour, 2008). This is known as endogenous stratification since the people to be surveyed are chosen using a stratified sampling strategy, with simple probability sampling within strata. The endogenous variable, in this case the number of trips to the site over a specific time period, defines the strata (Shaw, 1988). As a result, strata with a relatively large number of trips, or in other words, frequent visitors, have a higher likelihood of being represented in the sample, in proportion to their population size. In other words, even though the share of frequent visitors may be small in the population, on-site sampling may over-represent them in the sample, just as it may under-represent the less frequent visitors despite their relatively large share in the population.

If *Truncation* and *Endogenous Stratification* are not appropriately managed, they might lead to biased and inconsistent parameter estimations (Shaw, 1988). Endogenously stratified count data models are employed throughout the literature to remove these anomalies (e.g. Loomis, 2003; Hagerty and Moeltner, 2005; Bin et al., 2005; Espineira and Tuffour, 2008).

In the current study, the dependent variable is visitation rate i.e., number of times a visitor has taken a trip to DSNP over a span of five years, including the current trip. A span of 5 years has been considered since the number of visits per year by an individual to a single site for recreation is often not very high, except for a few purpose specific visitors. Since, the number of visits for most of the visitors will be a very small figure, visitation rate as a dependent variable will lack the desired variability for further econometric analysis. Keeping this in mind, to capture more variation in the data, visitation rate has been calculated over a period of 5 years. Works by Espineira and Tuffour (2008) and Barman (2012) have also adopted a similar strategy. Visitation rate, however, is a count variable, so ordinary least square estimation is not suitable. The referred models for count variables are usually the Poisson and the Negative binomial regression models. But because of a restrictive assumption of equi-dispersion i.e., equality of mean and variance, Poisson is sometimes claimed not suitable for recreational trip data, since this kind of data are usually believed to be over-dispersed with a variance greater than mean (Haab

and McConnell, 2002). For over-dispersed count data, the Negative binomial model is suggested as an alternative to Poisson (Tuffour and Espineira, 2008; Rodriguez, 2013). The Negative binomial distribution estimates a parameter α that can detect over-dispersion in the data, if any. In case of equi-dispersion, $\alpha = 0$, in case of over-dispersion, $\alpha > 0$ and in case of under-dispersion, $\alpha < 0$. Additionally, when $\alpha = 0$, the Negative binomial distribution collapses to Poisson distribution and produces same coefficients (Haab and McConnell, 2002; Mandal et al., 2014). Therefore, in the current study, first an experiment has been done and both Poisson and the Negative binomial distributions were fit into the survey data just to test for the presence of over-dispersion. The results show that the parameter estimates of both the models are similar (even down to their standard errors) and the null hypothesis of the likelihood ratio test, that says, $\alpha = 0$ cannot be rejected¹. Both these facts suggest presence of equi-dispersion and hence, Poisson has been selected as the suitable specification for the current dataset.

The density of the Poisson distribution for count y is given as:

$$\Pr(Y = y) = \frac{e^{-\mu}\mu^y}{y!}, \quad y = 0,1,2 \dots \dots \quad (1.1)$$

Where, the parameter μ is both the mean and the variance of the distribution. But as stated earlier, the on-site recreational survey data are truncated as zero. To account for this truncation, a truncated Poisson regression is usually applied. The density of the truncated Poisson is given as (Espineira and Tuffour, 2008):

$$\Pr(Y = y|Y > 0) = \frac{e^{-\mu}\mu^y}{y!} \left(\frac{1}{1 - e^{-\mu}} \right), \quad y = 1,2,3 \dots \dots \quad (1.2)$$

Finally, there is also the problem of endogenous stratification since the data was collected on-site. Now if the assumption of equi-dispersion holds true, the density of Poisson distribution truncated at zero and adjusted for endogenous stratification is (Shaw, 1988):

$$\Pr(Y = y|Y > 0) = \frac{e^{-\mu}\mu^{y-1}}{y - 1!}, \quad y = 1,2,3 \dots \dots \quad (1.3)$$

¹The results are presented in table A.1.in Appendix

So, it simply requires regressing $Y^* = Y - 1$ with a conventional Poisson regression model (Haab and McConnell, 2002). Hence, equation (1.3) represents the specified model to be used in the current recreational data. There are a few empirical works with the application of the model (Hesseln et al., 2003; Espineira et al., 2006; Mandal et al., 2014).

Explanatory Variables: The goal of ITCM is to estimate the demand for recreation in a particular site. To achieve this, respondents' visitation rate is regressed on travel cost along with a few other explanatory variables that may possibly affect visitation rate. The explanatory variables considered for the model are described below:

□ **Total Travel Cost (TTC):** Cost of travelling is the principal explanatory variable in any travel cost model. Where visitation rate implies the demand for recreation, travel cost implies the price of recreation. So, in line with the conventional demand analysis, an increase in travel cost, ceteris paribus, will lead to a decrease in visitation rate and vice versa. Almost all empirical studies have found this negative association between travel cost and visitation rate. The travel cost in the current study is named as total travel cost (TTC) which consists of out-of-pocket expenses of the respondents and the opportunity cost of time spent on travelling to DSNP. *Out-of-pocket expenses* include entry fee to the park with or without allowed appliances (whatever the case may be), round trip cost of transportation, cost of food and drink, cost of accommodation, if any, and safari charges.

Opportunity cost of travel time has been measured as the value of time saved on travelling so it could be spent on something else. Estimation of opportunity cost of time is a challenge in any travel cost model. Time is considered scarce since the time devoted to the trip to a recreational site could be spent on other activities, and hence, it has a cost. Empirically, the total time devoted to a trip is classified into two categories: (a) Time spent travelling and (b) Time spent on site. The opportunity cost of time dedicated to a particular activity depends on the alternative activities that have been traded off. Trading off work time can be measured by the wage or income forgone for a group of people. But it does not

work for everyone. For people who have a fixed work-time (i.e., those who cannot alternate between their work time and time for recreation), this poses a difficulty because they get engaged in recreation only when they are not working or not engaging in income earning activities. Valuing that time at wage rate for this section of people, therefore, is not a reasonable argument. Also, for people who do not participate in the labour market (for example students, home-makers etc.), the alternative use of time is not working for income, but for activities that do not get translated into any market-related price or wage. So, for this group of people as well, the time spent on recreation cannot be substituted for wage and their marginal cost of time therefore is not directly related to wage rate (Ovaskainen, et al., 2012). Since, both these groups of people constitute a sizeable part of the population, valuing time cost at wage rate is not justifiable. In this context, stated preference methods can help by providing a hypothetical market to trade time for money. Through stated preference methods, it is possible to calculate the willingness to pay of the visitors, which is basically a part of their income that they are willing to let go to reduce or save time spent on an activity. The core of the idea is that, the value of time reduced or saved in a particular activity is the value of time gained for an alternative activity and thus is the opportunity cost of time. On the basis of an insight from Ovaskainen, et al., (2012), a stated preference approach has been adopted to measure the opportunity cost of travel time or the value of travel time saved. Data on time spent on travel (in hours) for each respondent was recorded. The respondents were then enquired whether the time spent on travelling appeared to them as (a) a benefit or a pleasant part of the visit, (b) a cost or an unpleasant part of the visit, or (c) neither cost nor benefit, while deciding to travel to DSNP. Table 1.1 provides the percentage of answers against each option.

Table 1.1
Respondents' Perceptions about Travel Time

Option	Percentage
(a) Pleasant or benefit	34
(b) Unpleasant or a cost	6
(c) Indifferent; neither cost nor benefit	60

Source: Author's computation from field survey

On receiving either option (b) or (c) as the answer, the respondents were further presented with the following question:

Let, a project to build a new route from your place of residence or the place of departure to DSNP is proposed which will cut your travel time down to half of the present. The project will be financed through raising entry fee into the park collected over a period of 10 years. How much extra entry fee are you willing to pay at most for reducing travel time per visit? _____

Only about 10% of the respondents stated a positive willingness to pay (WTP) as an answer to this question. Majority perceived travel time as neither cost nor benefit and did not cite any WTP whereas, a sizeable number of respondents perceived travel time as a pleasant part of the visit. Keeping in mind that the reported WTP is for saving half of the current travel time, the WTP per hour of travel time saved has been calculated. This value is then multiplied by the total hours of time spent on travel to get the total opportunity cost of travel time². This kind of approach has a notable merit since it takes into account the recreationists' own individual perceptions of whether travel time is a cost or part of the experience, rather than assigning a standardized or imputed hourly cost (Ovaskainen, et al., 2012).

Measuring *opportunity cost of time spent on site* is however more challenging. Because of reasons aforesaid, it is not possible for everyone to trade time for money and hence, time cannot be exchanged against wage or income for every recreationist. However, even if this exchange of time and wage/income was possible for everyone, there would still be problem in using these wage/income figures to measure opportunity cost of on-site time. The opportunity cost of on-site time is usually less than the actual wage/income sacrificed, since the benefit received from recreation is over and above the benefit from wage/income forgone

² For the respondents who expressed the time spent on travelling to DSNP as a pleasant part of the visit or benefit, the willingness to pay distribution could not be known and hence, a zero value was assigned to their opportunity cost of travel time.

(Kolstad, 2006). This is evident from the fact that people not just sacrifice income, rather incur additional cost (such as on travel, accommodation etc.) in exchange for the on-site time. That is why the opportunity cost of on-site time is only some fraction of wage/income forgone. Different empirical works have tried using different fractions of wage/income for the purpose. But there is still no unanimous agreement on a definite figure. The idea of 'value of time saved' too is not very plausible in case of on-site time on similar grounds. Because of a comparatively larger benefit from recreation, most of the recreationists would not regard the time on site as a cost and therefore would not want to save it. With these reasons in place, the current study has to assume the opportunity cost of on-site time to be zero.

Another critical issue in calculation of total travel cost is the *presence of multi-site visitors*. Many a time, visitors' visits to a particular site might be part of a package tour; or in other words, their visits to the site in question may constitute only a part of the purpose of their journey (Hanley et al., 1997). In that case, not the entire cost of travelling, rather a portion of it should be attributed to the valuation of the site of interest. But for lack of a proper and universally agreed upon technique to alienate the part of total travel cost, multi-site visitors are often excluded from the sample. Doing so however, creates a sizeable information loss since the number of such multi-site visitors (especially visitors from distant areas who like to travel in packages) is not insignificant. People like to take the opportunity of tour packages where destinations that are relatively in close proximity to each other are clubbed together, to save on time and cost of travelling. In the current study, on the basis of an idea initiated by Hanley and Ruffell, (1993), an attempt has been made to isolate the part of the travel cost attributed to DSNP from the total cost of the packaged tour, when encountered with a multi-site visitor. To identify these visitors, first a question was raised enquiring whether the respondents' trip to DSNP is a part of a packaged tour. On receiving a 'yes' response, they were asked to rank their visit to DSNP on the basis of priority, out of the total number of places in the package. Data on total cost of the packaged tour was collected. With the help of rank reciprocal approach, the stated ranks of the respondents were converted into weights assigned

to their visit to DSNP. Rank reciprocal weights (W_i) are derived from the normalized reciprocals of an attribute's rank, the expression for which is (Stillwell et.al, 1981):

$$W_i = \frac{\frac{1}{R_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{1}{R_j}}$$

where,

W_i is the normalized weight for visit to DSNP

R_i is the rank assigned to the visit to DSNP

N is the number of places in the packaged tour

The sum total of the normalized rank reciprocal weights is equal to one. Therefore, the share of travel cost attributed to a multi-purpose visitor's trip to a site can be calculated by multiplying the total travel cost of the packaged tour by W_i . This has been followed in the current study to calculate the cost attributed to travel to DSNP for each multi-site visitor encountered.

Finally, if reported total travel costs relate to more than one individual, it has been converted to per head cost and included in the model.

□ **Distance (DIST):** Distance from the place of residence of the respondent or from the place of departure to DSNP is assumed to have a negative effect on visitation rate and included in the model. Usually distance is often associated with transportation cost; if distance increases, so does costs on transportation. That's why there may remain possible grounds for debate on inclusion of distance as a separate explanatory variable when round trip transportation cost is already included in TTC. In response, there are two reasons. *First*, apart from distance, transportation cost also depends on individual choices and available opportunities regarding say, routes and modes of transportation etc. Therefore, the monetary value of transportation cost may not always capture the effect of physical distance accurately. *Second*, in our study, TTC encompasses a hoard of other out-of-pocket expenses and the opportunity cost of time along with transportation cost. Therefore, the effect of physical distance on visitation rate cannot be isolated from TTC. Hence, it was felt that not including distance as an independent variable may reduce the

explanatory power of the model³. Distant travellers are expected to be less frequent visitors than visitors from nearby areas and hence the a priori expectation about the sign of the coefficient is negative.

□ **Consumption Standard Index (CSI):** Income is assumed to be an important determinant of visitation rate as higher income increases the ability to demand more recreation. In many empirical studies, the association between income and visitation rate has been a subject of investigation (Bin et al., 2005; Khan, 2006; Blackwell, 2007; Chae et al., 2012; Emiriya et al., 2013). But because of the reluctance of people to disclose information on their income figures, data on income is not easily available. In this study, a consumption standard index has been prepared as a proxy for income. Respondents were enquired about their possession of six specific consumer durables. On possession of all the six durables, CSI takes the value 1, on possession of none, CSI becomes 0 and for all intermediate cases, CSI is a positive fraction. The CSI for respondent i has been calculated as:

$$CSI_i = \frac{\text{Number of consumer durables in possession of respondent } i}{\text{Total number of consumer durables}}$$

It is reasonable to expect that CSI has a strong positive correlation with income.

□ **Substitute Site (SUB):** Theoretically, substitute price has a positive effect on quantity demanded. There are many empirical works that have included the effect of substitute sites as a probable covariate in regression models specified for identifying determinants of visitation rate (Himayatullah, 2003; Khan, 2006; Twerefou and Ababio, 2012; Tuffour and Espineira, 2008). Initially in the current study, an attempt was made to include the distance and cost of travelling to the substitute sites of DSNP. However, when a question was introduced enquiring whether the respondents know any other national park or protected area that they would like to

³The inclusion of distance is further justified from the observed absence of its multicollinearity with any other explanatory variable as evident from table 1.2

visit instead of visiting DSNP, many of them reported a 'no'⁴. Therefore, data on distance and travel cost to substitute sites were not available for this group of people. As a result of which, to capture the effect of substitute sites, only a dummy variable SUB has been included in the model. SUB takes the value 0 if respondents do not report a substitute site and 1 if they do. The a priori expectation about the sign of the coefficient is negative because in this case, SUB only denotes the status of availability of a substitute site rather than the distance or cost of travelling to that site. A negative sign conforms to the notion that availability of a substitute reduces quantity demanded.

□ **Age of the Respondent (AGE):** Age has been another factor that went through repeated empirical scrutiny in connection to its association with visitation rate (Poor and Smith, 2004; Rafiq and Shafiqullah, 2007; Twerefou and Ababio, 2012; Bharali and Mazumdar, 2012; Bhatt and Bhat, 2016). To examine the effect of age on visitation rate, age of the respondents in years, has been added as an explanatory variable in the regression model. On the assumption that, younger people tend to travel more than older people, AGE is expected to have a negative effect on visitation rate.

□ **Gender (GEN):** To determine the impact of gender of the respondent on the visitation rate, if any, it has been included as a dummy explanatory variable in the model. When the respondent is a female, GEN takes the value 0, when the respondent is a male, GEN takes the value 1. Empirically the association between gender and visitation rate has been studied by Barman, (2012), Twerefou and Ababio, (2012) and Mandal et al., (2014) among others. The empirical findings regarding gender and visitation rate are however inconsistent. Therefore, the expectation about the sign of the coefficient in the current study is uncertain a priori. It can move either way.

⁴This perhaps indicates to the fact that not all recreational services of DSNP are substitutable, at least to some visitors and hence they could not readily come up with an answer.

□ **Site Congestion (SC):** Quality of the site may also affect the visitation rate of the respondents. In the current study, site congestion or SC has been included as a measure of quality of the park as it can impact the quality of the recreational experience (Bin et al., 2005). However, congestion is a subjective phenomenon since it is difficult to predict how many people per square kilometre is actually perceived as a congestion by a random individual. Moreover, although, the effect of congestion on visitation rate is often assumed to be negative; sometimes, higher number of people in a particular site can actually increase the level of visitor satisfaction (Ditton et al., 1983). Specially, in situations where visitors are anticipating, if not desiring, crowds to be a part of their travel experience, congestion could be having a positive association (Bin et al., 2005). Therefore, in the current study visitor’s perception about congestion has been recorded. An enquiry was made whether they feel their trip satisfaction is adversely getting affected by congestion in DSNP. SC takes the value 0 if the response is ‘no’ and 1 if the response is ‘yes’. The a priori expectation about the sign of the coefficient is negative.

□ **Education (EDN):** Another respondent specific characteristic that has been widely studied across literature in connection to its effect on visitation rate is education (Himayatullah, 2003; Khan, 2006; Espineira and Tuffour, 2008; Barman, 2012). To examine the effect of education on the visitation rate, educational attainment of the respondent (in years), EDN has been included as another explanatory variable. The a priori expectation about the sign of the coefficient is positive i.e., higher the value of EDN, higher should be the value of visitation rate.

□ **Location of Residence (LOC):** Location of residence of the respondents may also have an effect on the visitation rate. Empirically a few studies have tried to examine the relationship between location of residence and visitation rate (for example, Himayatullah, 2003; Khan, 2006; Barman, 2012, Mandal et al., 2014). The empirical results however are not always consistent. To examine whether there is any difference between the visitation rate of respondents from urban and rural areas, LOC has been introduced as a dummy variable. When the location of residence is rural, LOC is equal to 0; when location of residence is urban, LOC is equal to 1. The a priori expectation about the sign of the coefficient is positive.

4. Results of Estimation and Interpretation: Before running the actual regression, the data have been tested for the possible presence of multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity.

To test for Multicollinearity, the Variance Inflating Factors (VIF) have been found out and reported in table 1.2

Table 1.2
Variance Inflating Factors of the Explanatory Variables

Variable	VIF
TTC	2.124
DIST	1.773
CSI	1.171
SUB	1.095
AGE	1.612
GEN	1.228
SC	1.133
EDN	1.049
LOC	1.198

Source: Author’s computation from field survey

As a rule of thumb, VIFs greater than 5 indicate presence of multicollinearity. From table 6.4, it is evident that the VIFs of all the independent variables are well below the cut off mark and hence the dataset is free from multicollinearity.

To check for the possible presence of heteroscedasticity, the Breusch Pagan (BP) test has been performed and the results are presented in table 1.3

Table 1.3
Results of BP test for Detection of Heteroscedasticity

H ₀ : Constant variance	
Chi square (9)	87.43
Prob > chi square	.000

Source: Author’s computation from field survey

The BP test rejects the null hypothesis of constant variance of the error term at 0.01 level of significance, hence detecting the presence of heteroscedasticity. Therefore, as a remedial measure, the regression has been run with robust standard errors. Table 1.4 presents the results of estimation.

Table 1.4
Results of Endogenously Stratified Truncated Poisson Model

Variables	Coefficients
TTC	-.00015*** (.00003)
DIST	-.00262*** (.0006)
CSI	.03104 (.24985)
SUB	-.28829*** (.08492)
AGE	-.01292** (.0065)
GEN	.18337 (.13687)
SC	-.26592** (.11572)
EDN	.01802 (.01350)
LOC	.38634** (.19530)
Constant	1.02928*** (.41307)
Number of observations = 211 Wald chi square[9] = 266.54*** Pseudo R square = 0.3156	

Note: figures in the parentheses are robust standard errors
 *** and ** indicate significance of the coefficients at 0.01 and 0.05 levels respectively
 Source: Author's computation from field survey

In table 1.4, the Wald chi square is significant which indicates that the model is a better fit over a null model. Two additional post-estimation tests i.e., Deviance goodness of fit and Pearson goodness of fit were carried out to check the fit of the model and the results are presented in table 1.5

Table 1.5
Results of Deviance goodness of fit and Pearson goodness of fit

Test	Results
Deviance goodness of fit	105.9974
Prob > chi square [201]	1.0000
Pearson goodness of fit	98.2089
Prob > chi square [201]	1.0000

Source: Author's computation from field survey

Table 1.5 indicates that the test statistics of both Deviance goodness of fit and Pearson goodness of fit are not significant. Non-significance of both the test statistics is indicative of a good model fit. Hence, it can be expected that fit of the model in the study is good.

An interesting finding in table 1.4 is that CSI is not significant. In this study, CSI was used as a proxy for income. The influence of income is found to be empirically inconsistent in travel cost studies. While studies with the desired positive income coefficients are there (Bin et al., 2005; Espineira and Tuffour, 2008; Barman, 2012), many studies found the effect of income negative or insignificant (Loomis, 2003; Creel and Loomis, 1990; Poor and Smith, 2004; Chae et al., 2012). In the current study, the variability of CSI was not quite high with a standard deviation of only 0.17 (which is quite low for a variable that ranges from 0 to 1 and has a mean of 0.72). Recreational trips commonly necessitate a minimum level of affordability on the part of the visitors (to cover the cost of travelling without jeopardising other essentials in the household budget), which may exclude certain income brackets at the lower end of the income spectrum from the group of visitors and reduce the factor's variability. This explanation also applies to the current study. The variability

in CSI was not adequate to have a significant effect on visitation rate in the presence of other stronger explanatory variables.

GEN is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference in the visitation rate of the male and female visitors and their gender do not significantly affect their visitation rate. EDN is also not significant indicating the educational attainment of the respondents do not have a significant effect on their visitation rate.

All the other explanatory variables in the model are significant and have retained their expected signs.

TTC is the most important variable in a Travel cost model. The coefficient of TTC is significant and negative, hence falls in line with the demand law and indicates that with increase in the cost of travelling, visitation rate, which in this case measures demand for recreation, decreases. The finding is theoretically plausible and empirically robust. Almost all studies on TCM report cost of travelling as a significant factor in determining visitation rate.

Among the other covariates, DIST is significant and negative and indicates that distant travellers visit less frequently than their counterparts in proximity to the site. Visit to a distant site often requires more planning and resources that may dampen the demand, when compared to visit to a nearby site. Hence, people end up travelling to distant places less frequently, especially when the goal is only recreation. Thus, the finding supports the coherent and rational human behaviours and decisions.

SUB is significant and negative. Respondents who reported a substitute site that they thought they would visit instead of visiting DSNP (SUB = 1) are less frequent travelers to the site than their counterparts (SUB = 0). This indicates that availability of a substitute site has a negative effect on visitation rate to DSNP. In other words, when people perceive the recreational services of DSNP as not unique and rather substitutable, they tend to visit less and vice versa.

AGE is significant and negative indicating younger people tend to visit DSNP more than older people. When people age, usually travelling for recreation becomes

relatively inconvenient with health and mobility issues. As a result of which their share in demand for recreation is low in proportion to the younger people.

SC is significant and negative. Site congestion was included as a measure of site quality in the model. Respondents who feel that congestion in DSNP is reducing their satisfaction (SC = 1), tend to visit less than their counterparts (SC = 0). This implies that perceived quality of the park by the visitors affects visitation rate. When they perceive the quality to be good in a way that enhances or at least do not reduce their recreational utility, they tend to visit more.

LOC is significant and positive. This indicates that people from urban areas (LOC = 1) tend to visit DSNP more than those from the rural areas (LOC = 0). In rural places people usually live in closer proximity to nature whereas, in urban areas proximity to nature is relatively low. Consequently, the scarcity value of nature may be comparatively higher for the urban people which may encourage them to visit more often to such natural sites. DSNP is a protected natural area and the larger share of the urbanites in the demand for its recreational services might stem from a similar reason.

Consumer Surplus: In a single site model, the coefficient of TTC or the estimated price coefficient in the recreational demand model gives us the estimate of consumer surplus. Thus, the coefficient of TTC, reported in table 1.4 can be used to calculate the consumer surplus that the visitors of DSNP derive from having access to the park. The consumer surplus per trip can be calculated as $-\frac{1}{\beta_{TTC}}$ (Creel and Loomis, 1990; Yen and Adamowicz, 1993; Espineira and Tuffour, 2008). Multiplying this expression by the sample mean visitation rate, we get the sample mean consumer surplus (Haab and McConnell, 2002). Therefore, the sample mean consumer surplus in the present study for a span of 5 year is $\left(-\frac{1}{-.00015} \times 2.06\right) = \text{INR } 13,733.33$. To get the population figure of the welfare estimate, the sample mean has to be aggregated over the population. The total number of visitors into DSNP over the period of five years preceding the survey turned out to be 16,983 after calculation⁵.

⁵Calculated by author using data from Economic Survey, Assam, 2017-18

Therefore, the consumer surplus for the population is estimated at around INR 23.32 crores for five years. Dividing this figure by 5 we get its annual equivalent which is around INR 4.7 crores.

5. Conclusion: The annual average revenue collection on arrival of tourists for the period of five years preceding the survey is around INR 1.14 lakhs⁶. This is only about 0.24% of the total consumer surplus of the visitors of the park. This answers the question that *the existing user charges of DSNP cannot reflect the true recreational demand of the park by its visitors*. Considering this, it can be stated that the recreational services of the park are severely underpriced and there is sufficient scope for raising the revenue collection on arrival of tourists by increasing the user charges.

The findings of the study are expected to be useful for different stakeholders associated with the park's conservation in general and its recreational services in particular, including policymakers. Apart from revision of user charges, the findings can also be used to justify the need for additional resource allocation to boost conservation efforts and enhance the recreational amenities of the park. Although the analysis in the present study focuses on the demand side of recreation, its findings can also be used as a guide by the stakeholders on the supply side, such as boat owners, owners of lodges and resorts in the park's surrounding areas, local transportation agencies, and others who largely rely on the visitors of DSNP, to further improve the quality of their services and attract an even larger tourist flow.

The estimates in the study should be considered rather as lower bounds of the recreational demand for one valid reason: while estimating the total travel cost, the study has to assume the opportunity cost of on-site time to be zero for lack of a proper measuring scale. Had this been calculated, the recreational value would have been higher than what currently stands. The study also could not properly capture the effect of distance and cost of travelling to substitute sites, since many of the visitors did not mention any substitute site that they would travel to instead of

⁶Calculated by author using data from Economic Survey, Assam, 2017-18

DSNP. Therefore, the effect of substitute site could only be examined from the perspective of availability (with the help of a dummy variable) rather than from the perspective of accessibility. However, viewing from a different angle, a more reasonable explanation can be provided that some recreational services of the park may be truly unique in nature and hence not substitutable, at least to some visitors, for which, they could not readily come up with the name of a substitute site.

To conclude, it has to be admitted that, like most of the valuation studies, the analysis in the study too is only from the demand perspective. To uncover the full potential of recreation, visitors' post visit feedbacks and experiences will also have to be taken into account so that the services associated to the supply side of recreation could be enhanced to attract more tourists.

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Appendix

Table A-1 Results of Poisson and Negative binomial distribution models

Variables	Poisson	Negative Binomial
TTC	-.00007** (.00003)	-.00007** (.00003)
DIST	-.00085* (.00048)	-.00085* (.00048)
CSI	.16629 (.31797)	.16629 (.31797)
SUB	-.22832** (.11401)	-.22832** (.11401)
AGE	-.00582 (.00572)	-.00582 (.00572)
GEN	.11665 (.12568)	.11665 (.12568)
SC	-.16628 (.11750)	-.16628 (.11750)
EDN	.00951 (.01721)	.00951 (.01721)
LOC	.18171 (.13671)	.18171 (.13671)
Constant	1.14308*** (.42206)	1.14308*** (.42206)
alpha		3.63e ⁻¹² ≈.00002
Likelihood ratio test of alpha = 0		Chi bar square (01) = 0.00 Prob>= Chi bar square = 1.000
	No. of observations = 211 Wald chi square[9] = 90.57*** Pseudo R square = 0.1370 Log likelihood = -285.37	No. of observations = 211 Wald chi square[9] = 90.57*** Pseudo R square = 0.1370 Log likelihood = -285.37

Source : Author's Computation from field survey.